

Comparing Promotability Outlooks: Industry Professionals vs. MBA Student Perspectives

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Abstract

In career advancement research, understanding the nuanced perceptions of promotability is crucial for both Industry Professionals and MBA students aspiring to navigate the professional landscape. The result of this study delves into the methodological nuances of comparing promotability perceptions between these two distinct cohorts, employing the permutation methods as a robust and effective technique, which confirmed the result of the T-test and Cohens d. The permutations method, a nonparametric approach, excels in situations where traditional parametric methods fall short, especially when dealing with small sample sizes and non-normal distributions. There were 31 students and 27 organizations involved in the study. The High Potential Employees (HiPos) is the theoretical framework used to examine the gap between the rating of Industry professionals and MBA students' self-rating. The researcher is interested in identifying the indicators with the widest gap. Learning agility and leadership spirit were the top two indicators with the most extensive positive difference, while turnover intention was the only indicator with a negative difference. Notably, turnover intention and job engagement were the two indicators with a significant statistical difference in rating between MBA students and Industry Professionals. Also, job engagement depicts the highest Cohen's d size comparison. The result of this study unravels the intricacies of the perceived promotability of MBA students based on their self-rating and the industry professionals' perceptions.

Keywords: *High potential employees (HiPos), MBA students, Industry Professionals, Permutations, UNSDG 8.*

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Introduction

Very few studies quantitatively measured the promotability of students who finished their business graduate education using the dimensions of high potential employees (HiPos). Previous research presented characteristics and traits depicting HiPos personalities, characters, and competence, but the results focused only on concepts

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and theories. For instance, the latest researchers emphasize identifying and developing high-potential employees within their organization (Gelens et al., 2014); (Downs, 2015); (Dries & De Gieter, 2014). These investigations provided different techniques for identifying HiPos. They suggested methods for implementing high-potential employee development programs, which revolve around three critical dimensions: drive for excellence, strong leadership spirit, and learning orientation. H.R. managers considered HiPos identification, facilitation, and management to pose many challenges (Rebet'ák & Farkašová, 2015). Precise HiPos identification is essential as it affects the potential promotion of an employee (Gelens et al., 2014).

Organizations design and seek a system for identifying high-potential employees. Line managers were the best people in the organization to identify and provide development opportunities to HiPos (Fulmer et al., 2009). The criteria for identifying HIPO are essential for several organizations to try to augment their selection with talent companies (Church et al., 2015). Specifically, the search involves gathering top-down input from different organizational people to identify top potential employees. Later, a committee decides to identify HiPos (Dries & Pepermans, 2012).

After identifying high-potential employees, the organization often offers them unique development opportunities such as an MBA education (Church et al., 2015), special incentives, and exclusive benefits immediately after identification (Dries & De Gieter, 2014). Frequently, organizations offer the MBA program to high-potential employees or perceive MBA students as HiPo (Dreher & Ryan, 2002).

The stiff competition among organizations to get the best talents to become successors is pertinent to present management. The organization wanted to develop their high-potential employees to assume leadership positions and, therefore, be willing to invest in development programs. The desire of the organization to sustain its competitiveness is the main reason for preparing HiPos for a future executive position. On the other hand, MBA students and graduates wanted to advance their career paths (Ballou et al., 1999), opting to adopt change strategies and transformative approaches to achieve their career goals (Al Ariss, 2010).

At this point, it is essential to identify the different dimensions of HiPos the employer and MBA students prioritize to determine the promotability gap. The main objective of comparing the perceived HiPos of MBA students and Industry Professionals is to gauge the accuracy and potential strengths and weaknesses in HiPos of the MBA students. A calibrated adjustment on the priority of the MBA students can help Professional Schools design a curriculum that focuses on the HiPos dimension based on the lens of the employers. It indicates that even if MBA students have the qualities to assume a higher executive position if they need more characteristics, employers expect their true potential is unlikely to be unleashed.

Managers will likely assign high-position employees with excellent performance. MBA students cannot merely rely on the performance appraisal that identifies an employee's potential since successive higher-level position needs a unique set of skills, and considering past and present performance is not enough (Rebet'ák & Farkašová, 2015). In this case, the management assessed the MBA student's potential qualities for higher positions. Therefore, the management identified the HiPos dimension and made a critical decision in promoting MBA graduates.

Currently, the performance appraisal of employees remains the most common method to determine if they possess enough potential for a higher position. The problem is that some top performers may need to recognize their potential (De Meuse, Dai &

Hallenbeck, 2010). For many years, many top performers missed their turn to be promoted because of their inability to acknowledge the prioritized HiPos dimension of their employer. Others lost their chance due to their refusal to transition from their prioritized HiPos dimension to their employer. They must acknowledge that they manage their potential employee paradigm (Juhdi et al., 2012).

Review of Literature

High-potential employees (HiPos) are those with the potential to hold critical leadership roles in the future and are vital for the growth and sustainability of any organization. There are several benefits or advantages of HiPos in the organization. As precious assets to any organization, HiPos significantly impacts the organization's performance, productivity, and profitability (Dries & Pepermans, 2012). HiPos drives innovation, quality, and customer satisfaction, creating a culture of excellence and collaboration, filling the leadership pipeline, and ensuring the continuity and stability of the organization. With their exceptional characteristics, HiPos excels in their roles and goes above and beyond expectations, allowing them to leverage their brands to add value and get noticed by the organization (Juhdi et al., 2012).

Identifying high-potential employees allows for targeted personnel development, investing in their career path, teaching them new skills, and providing opportunities for employee engagement and leadership experiences (Rebet'ák & Farkašová, 2015) – subsequently increasing employee retention, motivation, and satisfaction, including reducing turnover costs and risks. HiPos earns the trust and respect of others by demonstrating high levels of consistency and professionalism, keeping their word, and delivering results. They assume their goals and responsibilities seriously and often exceed the expectations and standards of their role (Malik & Singh, 2014).

Drive for High Performance is how employees exceed expectations and standards for their high role. MBA students driven by the pursuit of personal and professional excellence exhibit a commitment to continuous learning, a desire for career advancement, and deep-seated ambition for leadership roles (Abraham et al., 2016). Attributed to the academic environment, characterized by rigorous curriculum and peer competition, further intensifies the drive. The complex interaction of aspiration, educational environments, and career goals sustains the unwavering commitment of MBA students to excel in their endeavors.

Organizational engagement is the degree to which employees feel connected to and committed to their organization. HiPos is engaged with its organization's vision, values, and culture and is willing to contribute to its success (Kamel, 2019, November). Evidence reveals that MBA students undergo a transformative educational journey, developing a deep commitment to organizations. Incorporating robust academic rigor and experiential learning in MBA programs fosters a strong sense of belonging and identification with their future organizational context (Khoreva & van Zalk, 2016). Underscored is the reciprocal nature of support and commitment from MBA students, perceiving tangible and intangible support from educational institutions and potential employers alike and responding with increased organizational commitment.

Learning agility is learning from experience and applying the learning to new and unique situations. HiPos are adaptable and flexible, adjusting to change and uncertainty, curious, and seeking feedback to improve their learning (Church, 2021). MBA students are often exposed to diverse learning experiences and a future-ready

curriculum, empowering their agility in a volatile environment. Also, MBA students have mental agility, which is the ability to learn new information from different sources and make connections between seemingly unrelated concepts. Mental agility helps MBA students adapt to new situations and learn quickly, which is valuable in today's fast-paced business environment (Milani et al., 2021).

The likelihood that an employee will voluntarily leave their organization shortly is described as the turnover intention. A lower turnover intention than average employees is observed among HiPos attributed to their higher level of satisfaction and loyalty to their organization and less likely attracted to other opportunities as they perceived a clear career path within their organization (Thomas & Letchmiah, 2017). Factors such as work-life balance, job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and career development opportunities influence turnover intention. MBA students who are working professionals pursuing a higher degree have lower turnover intention than other employees because of different motivations and expectations for their work and education (Van Der Zee, 2016). MBA students seek to enhance their skills, knowledge, and network through their studies and perceive their current work as a means to support their learning and career goals. Also, MBA students have a higher sense of loyalty and gratitude to their organization, especially if they receive financial or moral support from their employer (Fritsch, 2018). Moreover, MBA students project a lower desire to change their jobs as they face more challenges and uncertainties in the job market than other employees. Thus, MBA students have lower turnover intention than other employees, as they are more satisfied and committed to their work and education and perceive a better career in their organization (Saul, 2016).

Leadership spirit is the willingness and capability to take on leadership roles and responsibilities. With a strong sense of self-awareness, emotional intelligence, and strategic thinking, HiPos present a high leadership potential, and they often stand out for their ability to lead, influence, and inspire others (Ibadat, 2023, March). The confluence of rigorous academic challenges, experiential learning opportunities, and exposure to diverse perspectives encourage a proactive and visionary mindset among MBA students, enhancing their propensity for leadership roles. Furthermore, the emphasis on collaborative learning and the cultivation of soft skills within MBA programs contribute to developing adaptive and inspirational leadership qualities (Winiarska-Januszewicz & Winiarski, 2014).

HiPos often go above and beyond their duties, displaying a positive attitude and level of attitude. They are passionate and energized in their work to the extent that they are absorbed in and enthusiastic about it, also known as job engagement (Khoreva & van Zalk, 2016). MBA students tend to display a higher job engagement due to several factors. MBA programs furnish students with future-ready curricula and diverse learning experiences, which help them develop a strong sense of belonging and purpose in their work (Juhdi et al., 2012). A sense of purpose as intrinsic motivation increases job engagement. Also, MBA students are exposed to opportunities for professional development and growth, which can enhance their skills and contribute to their job engagement. Further, MBA students often have a higher level of mental agility, allowing them to adapt to new situations and learn quickly in a fast-paced business environment, helping them stay engaged and motivated in their work. Lastly, MBA students know the importance of employee engagement and actively seek opportunities to engage in their work and organization (Dries & Pepermans, 2012).

HiPos's paradigm identifies and develops high-potential employees within an organization that aligns with several U.N. Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

However, the specific alignment depends on the program's design and objectives connected with SDG 8: decent Work and Economic Growth, which is "to achieve full and productive employment and decent work for all women and men including for young people and PWDs and equal pay for work of equal value." HiPos contributes to creating quality jobs and promoting equal opportunities for advancement by focusing on developing high-performance talent. Also, HiPos builds leadership capacity, promotes organizational growth, and contributes to sustainable economic development, focusing on innovation, problem-solving, and ethical decision-making, which align with creating a decent and sustainable workplace.

Materials and Methods

The initial analysis involved extracting the difference between the MBA students self-rating and the industry rating. A positive difference indicated that the MBA students had overrated themselves, while a negative difference meant they had underrated themselves. The difference technique was used to compare the two groups.

In determining the significant difference between the MBA student's self-rate and industry ratings in the HiPos areas of the drive for high performance, organizational engagement, learning agility, turnover intention, leadership spirit, and job engagement, the paired t-test was used. The method was used to know whether significant gap differences existed between the two groups.

The study used an adapted questionnaire from Juhdi et al. (2012) entitled Examining Characteristics of High Potential Employees from Employees' Perspective. The study involved 31 MBA students and 27 organizations and was conducted from January 30 to April 30, 2023.

Permutation was the method used to determine the significant difference in the promotability perception between the industry and students. A permutation test is whether the difference between two groups is statistically significant or attributed to chance (Berry et al., 2011). In this case, two groups are the industry practitioners and MBA students' ratings of promotability perception. The permutation test involved the following steps: calculate the observed difference in the mean ratings between the two groups, and the test statistics are denoted by T . All the ratings were pooled together and randomly assigned to two groups of the same size as the original groups. The difference in mean ratings for this permutation was determined 10,000 times to obtain a distribution of the test statistics showing no significant difference between the two groups (Good, 2013). The observed test statistics were compared with the distribution from the permutations. The proportion of permutations with test statistics as extreme or more extreme than the observed data, which is the p-value of the test, measures the probability of observing such a difference by chance alone (Wu et al., 2016).

The permutation test was based on the assumption that the ratings are exchangeable, signifying the possibility of assigning to either group without affecting the distribution, which is reasonable if the ratings are independent and identically distributed (Leem & Park, 2018, December). The permutation test is a nonparametric method that does not depend on any specific distribution or parametric model for the data. Also, it is a resampling method, using the data to generate the null distribution. These features make the permutation test more flexible and robust than other methods, such as the t-test (Proschan et al., 2014).

Further, Cohen's D was used to measure the effect size that compares the difference between MBA students and Industry Professionals regarding standard deviation. Cohen's D was used to assess the magnitude and significance of the difference between the two groups by comparing it to a general guideline. According to Cohen, a D of 0.2 is a small effect; 0.5 is a medium effect, and 0.8 or higher is a large effect (Cahan & Gamliel, 2011).

Results

The primary objective of comparing the HiPos of MBA students' self-rating and Industry professionals' evaluations is to assess the accuracy of student self-perception and identify potential biases or blind spots in their understanding of their strengths and weaknesses as future leaders. Analyzing the discrepancies between self-ratings and industry assessments intends to promote the enhancement of the MBA curriculum.

Table 1 compares the ratings of MBA students and the industry on various aspects of promotability perception, such as Drive for High Performance, Organizational Engagement, Learning Agility, Turnover Intention, Leadership Agility, Turnover Intention, Leadership Spirit, and Job Engagement. The ratings are presented in mean and standard deviation. For the Drive for High Performance, Organizational Engagement, Learning Agility, Turnover Intention, Leadership Spirit, and Job Engagement, the industry rated higher than the MBA students. Industry experts rated MBA students in their organizations in terms of their higher potential characteristics than MBA students' self-rating. Depicted in Table 1 was the level of HiPo as the organization rated their Business Cluster graduates and as the graduates self-rated themselves. The widest gap existed in learning agility (M = 3.88; SD = 0.64; M = 4.24; 0.43); and leadership spirit (M = 3.73; SD = 0.61; M = 4.07; SD = 0.45) which the MBA graduates underrated themselves. The widest negative gap existed in the turnover intention (M = 3.12; SD = 0.61; M = 3.07; SD 0.45), in which the industry believed that their new MBA graduates eventually intended to resign and look for better opportunities.

Table 1. HiPos MBA students self-rating versus Industry Professionals

Aspect	MBA Mean	Industry Mean	MBA S.D.	Industry S.D.	GAP (Industry – MBA)
Drive for High Performance	4.05	4.29	0.58	0.42	0.24
Organizational Engagement	3.92	4.08	0.635	0.5	0.16
Learning Agility	3.88	4.24	0.64	0.43	0.36
Turnover Intention	3.12	3.07	0.61	1.09	-0.05
Leadership Spirit	3.73	4.07	0.61	0.45	0.34
Job Engagement	3.59	3.70	0.8	0.69	0.11

Table 2 below displays a statistical analysis comparing the promotability perception of MBA students and Industry Professionals considered high-potential employees. Promotability perceptions are the degree to which employees believe they have the skills, abilities, and potential to advance their careers. Two methods are used to test the significance difference between the two groups: the permutation test and the t-test. The permutation test is a nonparametric method that randomly shuffles the labels of

the groups and calculates the difference in means for each permutation. The p-value is the proportion of permutations that results in a difference equal to or more extreme than the observed difference. Conversely, the t-test is a parametric method that assumes the groups have equal variances and normal distribution and calculates the probability of obtaining a difference as large as the observed difference.

Table 2. Significance Test MBA Students versus Industry Professionals

Promotability Perception	Permutation p-value	T-test p-value	Mean Difference	Pooled Standard Deviation	Cohen's d	Decision on Ho
High Performance	0.321	0.689	0.026	0.087	-0.299 *	Do not reject
Organizational Engagement	0.413	0.372	0.022	0.089	0.247 *	Do not reject
Learning Agility	0.960	0.745	-0.001	0.175	0.006 *	Do not reject
Turnover Intention	0.020	0.014	0.068	0.097	-0.696 **	Reject
Leadership Spirit	0.828	0.895	-0.008	0.071	0.113 *	Do not reject
Job engagement	0.006	0.005	-0.084	0.089	0.944 ***	Reject

0.2 small effect*; 0.5 medium effect**; 0.8 large effect***

Further, Table 2 shows the p-values, mean differences, pooled standard deviation, and Cohen's d-effect sizes for six variables related to promotability perception: high performance, organizational engagement, learning agility, turnover intention, leadership spirit, and job engagement. High performance is the extent to which an employee exceeds the expectations and standard of their role. Organizational engagement is how employees feel connected to and committed to their organization. Learning agility is learning from experience and applying that learning to new and different situations. Turnover intention is the likelihood of an employee voluntarily leaving their organization shortly. Leadership spirit is the willingness and capability to take on leadership roles and responsibilities. Job engagement is the extent to which employees are absorbed in and enthusiastic about their work.

Based on Table 2, the analysis found that there is a significant difference in the mean promotability perception between MBA students and industry professionals for two variables: turnover intention ($p < 0.05$) and job engagement ($p < 0.05$). For both variables, the permutations test and t-test resulted in p-values less than 0.05, conveying that the observed difference in means is unlikely to occur by chance. The mean difference for turnover intention is negative, contending that MBA students have a lower turnover intention than industry professionals. Conversely, the mean difference for job engagement is positive, conveying that MBA students have a higher job engagement than industry professionals. Moreover, the effect size for both variables is significant based on Cohen's d guidelines, suggesting that the difference in promotability perception between the two groups is significant.

The other four variables of high performance, organizational engagement, learning agility, and leadership spirit depict no significant difference in the mean promotability between students and industry professionals. In the case of these variables, the permutation test and the t-test resulted in p-values greater than 0.05, conveying that the observed difference in means is likely to occur by chance. The mean difference for these variables is small and close to zero, meaning that MBA students and industry professionals present similar levels of promotability perception for these variables. The

effect sizes for these variables are negligible based on Cohen's guidelines, indicating that the difference in promotability perception between the two groups is insignificant.

Discussion

The dissonance between the industry ratings of MBA students as HiPos and self-ratings by the students themselves can be attributed to several reasons. Individuals in the Industry often evaluate MBA students based on their observed performance, tangible skills, and demonstrated leadership abilities, concluding real-world experiences. In contrast, MBA students self-rate modestly due to a higher level of self-awareness, acknowledging areas of improvement or uncertainties about their potential. Also, industry professionals place a premium on practical, industry-specific skills and experiences, which always align with the self-perceived potential of MBA students who focus more on theoretical knowledge gained during their studies. Moreover, self-ratings are influenced by factors such as imposter syndrome, where individuals underestimate their abilities despite evidence of competence. The industry's perspective is often influenced by holistic evaluation that considers a candidate's ability to traverse complex challenges and contribute meaningfully to organizational goals. These gaps in perception focus on the need for effective communication and career development strategies that align individual self-perception with industry expectations.

The similarity between people in the Industry and MBA students considering the drive for high performance as a strength of MBA students arises from several considerations. MBA programs are designed to cultivate a culture of excellence and achievement, instilling a solid work ethic and drive for student success. The commitment to high performance results from the curriculum's rigorous nature and challenging assignments and projects. Due to the competitive nature of MBA programs, industry professionals recognize the students' motivation to excel academically and demonstrate their capacity in a highly competitive environment. The alignment in perceptions indicates that industry evaluators and MBA students acknowledge the importance of a proactive, result-oriented mindset in the business landscape. Further, the drive for high performance is highly wanted in potential employees, making it a shared point of recognition between industries.

Learning Agility

Depicted in Table 1 were the gaps between the MBA students and industry-preferred HIPO characteristics. The rating wherein the industry professionals rated higher than MBA students' self-rating is in the learning agility factor, demonstrating that the industry recognized that a significant critical component of high-potential employees is learning agility (Charan, 2005). MBA students are willing to learn, can execute complex strategies, are open to new experiences with high ambiguity tolerance, have good interpersonal skills, and possess excellent learning agility (De Meuse et al., 2010). The industry considered learning agility very important and predicted supervisory ratings.

Though insignificant, the gap was most prominent in the student's ability to proactively demonstrate that they are comfortable with any changes and adopt new things (Persson, 2014). The industry believed MBA students to be agile in adapting new business strategies (Ismail et al., 2011), calm in working across cultures (Hjarvard, 2013), at ease in dealing with project teams, and dedicated to accepting new assignments aside from their work flexibility. Practically, the industry valued the

learning-agile behavior of graduate students, especially those who were less defensive to criticism and sincere in welcoming feedback. Also, the industry wanted more reflective and willing employees to change.

Part of the learning agility was the different behaviors required across an organization's different levels and units. The industry knows that MBA students need to understand that effective behaviors in one unit do not necessarily lead to success in another (Sherehiy & Karwowski, 2014); furthermore, when the organization is undergoing a volatile phase, employees are expected to adapt more than ever. In terms of considering the long-term potential of MBA students, the industry placed primary importance on learning agility rather than the current set of skills, which they considered most important for the organization to respond to future challenges (Beechler & Woodward, 2009). Consequently, the industry expects to find from their MBA students the ability to give up ideas, perspectives, and skills that are no longer relevant and learn new ones (Wang & Beier, 2012).

Undoubtedly, MBA students possess mental agility, an inherent characteristic that shows their ability to scrutinize problems and concoct connections between different ideas (Wang & Beier, 2012). However, change agility, an essential element of learning ability appeared outside the industry's expectations. In the industry, MBA students are hesitant to experiment and cope effectively with the hardships of a volatile environment. Only some MBA students can deliver results in first-time situations (Bahrami et al., 2016).

Leaders identified risk-taking as the most difficult to pass within the organization (Kuratko et al., 2014). The industry also felt that MBA students are the same. The MBA student's openness to experience is one thing, and risk-taking is another. It was surprising to the Industry that MBA students remained defensive to negative, which reduces learning agility (Hogan et al., 2010). The industry expected MBA graduates to seek feedback, analyze it, and adjust themselves based on their understanding of the problem and situation. The industry considers risk-taking a necessary measure of highly successful managers highly associated with learning agility (Anseel, 2017).

The industry identified the lack of progressive risk as a weakness of MBA students. The industry considered MBA students hesitant to venture into uncertain environments and place themselves in an uncertain environment (Vecchiato, 2012). Although the industry considers progressive risk part of learning agility, MBA students are seldom pioneers and are uncomfortable with the risk that results in opportunity (A.V. & Aithal, 2018). Progressive risk is not thrill-seeking; instead, it is a calculated risk. Nonetheless, MBA graduates hesitate to undertake jobs and roles that do not guarantee success, and failure is possible. MBA graduates are unwilling to venture outside their comfort zone (Aimin, 2010).

MBA students consider performance matters. However, the hesitant attitude of MBA students to progressive risk led them to focus on their short-term performance at the cost of personal development (Wang et al., 2009). They should have realized that overusing their greatest strength can sometimes cause problems. The industry wanted MBA students to realize that accepting new challenges that force them to venture outside their comfort zones and develop new skills and ideas is vital to their future (Bhimani, 2009).

Leadership Spirit

Another HiPos element is that Industry Professionals rated higher than MBA students. The industry identified that the present market challenges, such as organizational agility, capability, and efficiency, required high creativity, productivity, and ownership (Gong & Janssen, 2012). Presently, there are two basic ways organizational efforts are designed to fail. First is the need for a whole system approach. Organizational efforts fail when the system fails to isolate the problem to be solved. Second, efforts could be more realistic and piecemeal. This approach is similar to treating the symptoms and not the disease. Thus, any short-term improvement is often followed by deteriorating long-term conditions. By far, the leading spirit in the organization is the most common way to change efforts to succeed.

The industry wanted MBA students to demonstrate leadership spirit in the organization significantly. Superficially, MBA students' efforts focus only on the external side of change (Talim, 2012). For example, when the organization introduces new technology accompanied by restructuring, temporary teams, revised policies, and a reward system, workflows are updated, which appears to be in place. However, these systems only work in the presence of a leadership spirit. Most change efforts fail because the system cannot organize, but leadership does (Crawford & Nahmias, 2010).

Equally, the industry observed that MBA students avoided power and played safe, demonstrating characteristics of loyalty and hardworking subordinates as a means to get protection and importance from their managers (Bakker et al., 2012). The industry wanted MBA students to take higher risks, manage conflict, make difficult decisions, and assume more responsibility and visibility (Too & Weaver, 2014). However, among MBA students, the mandate cast a crisis of identity.

The industry wanted to promote employees with leadership spirit to facilitate a profound internal change in the organization (Aragón-Correa et al., 2007). An excellent leadership spirit empowers high-performance teamwork, requiring each member to change their outmoded identity fundamentally, not merely adjust a few skills (Montes et al., 2005). Only an excellent leadership spirit can fundamentally create a new understanding of organizational change (Plowman et al., 2007).

Based on industry observations, MBA students struggled to adapt to any change in direction that required effort to meet essential goals (Lord & Brown, 2001). The industry needs help to place additional responsibilities and changes in priorities that focus on high-priority goals. Indeed, MBA students find it challenging to discuss their subordinates' responsibilities and enter into the jurisdictions of clear and specific outcomes, which include the definition and measure of success (Zhu et al., 2009).

Specifically, facilitation skills are desired among MBA students. They find it challenging to assist everyone in keeping communication open (Ladyshevsky, 2006). Also, the industry wanted the MBA students to ante up their facilitating skills, which means treading the thin line between being knowledgeable and helpful while engaged with the team but avoiding the role of an "expert," which has an effect of shifting away members' ideas and responsibilities (Mumford et al., 2000).

Leadership played a critical role in increasing the relationship between empowerment and performance. The industry needs MBA students to act as "coaches" who can promote an environment that inspires and encourages the ideal environment (Gao et al., 2011). There needs to be more MBA students and industry in encouraging subordinates to attain goals, improve performance to gain the latest competencies and

skills, or accept responsibilities (Rego et al., & e Cunha, 2012). More than MBA students, the industry believed that coaching improves leaders' effectiveness (Ely et al., 2010). However, due to the lackluster leadership spirit of MBA students, they could be more effective in managing teams, possess lower morale and mediocre bottom-line results below the industry's expected results, and might find themselves bypassed by other non-MBA employees (Aquila, 2001).

Generally, since MBA students needed more enthusiasm to assume a leadership coach, they were less effective in their leadership role in the organization, especially when there was a need to improve internal involvement (Hall et al., 1999). They seemed to practice a "command and control" type of management (Sonnenwald & Pierce, 2000). Unfortunately, MBA students can only extend minimal help in encouraging employees to grow, assume responsibility, and have the authority to improve the organization's quality of work.

Turnover Intention

It is challenging to promote an employee who explicitly demonstrates an intention to leave. The industry believes that MBA students have a firm turnover intention due to their higher educational qualifications (McKnight et al., 2009). Moreover, the industry supposed that the possible high turnover intention of MBA graduates manifests in their profound work commitment to the organization (Kim et al., 2016). Unsurprisingly, the industry invested significantly in policies and practices to promote engagement and commitment among their MBA students. A low level of engagement in the industry observed from MBA students may lead to a high turnover intention (Simpson, 2009).

The significant divergence in turnover intention between industry ratings of MBA students and self-rating by students themselves arises from different factors. Industry professionals considering MBA students as HiPos consider long-term commitment, adaptability, and alignment with organizational values. Contrarily, MBA students self-rate their turnover intention based on short-term considerations such as present personal aspirations, career exploration, or uncertainty about their post-MBA directions. Industry evaluations factor in the strategic value of retaining skilled and well-educated professionals, possibly leading to lower perceived turnover intentions. On the other hand, MBA students focus on immediate personal or career goals, potentially overestimating their likelihood of considering alternative opportunities. Effective communication between MBA students and industry professionals, including a shared understanding of career expectations and organizational fit, contributes to a more aligned perception of turnover intention.

The difference is attributed to higher education; the industry helps its employees attain the knowledge and skills they need to accomplish their jobs. Employees who improve their skills through MBA education are expected to be fully involved in their work since they derive satisfaction from their higher educational qualifications (Fruhen et al., 2014). The MBA degree enhanced the employees' value to the industry and their labor market value. Also, the industry is willing to offer higher remuneration for experts to compensate for their high labor market value and discourage turnover (Mihail & Kloutsiniotis, 2014).

There is a strong link between employee engagement and business outcomes. Employee engagements are positively associated with employees' loyalty, productivity, and turnover, including customer satisfaction. Employee engagement has the most substantial effect on employee turnover compared to customer satisfaction and safety.

A firm belief in the industry that their MBA students will look for better opportunities is due to the observed low employee engagement or better career offers from other organizations.

Similarly, employee attitudes are another element that can strongly determine turnover intention. Surprisingly, employee attitude has a weak association with productivity compared to employee turnover. In other words, the industry observed that the attitude changes would finally lead to turnover. However, the modest magnitude of the association between attitude and turnover translates into millions for MBA students with managerial positions.

Job Engagement

The disparity between the job engagement of MBA students self-rating and the assessments industry professionals provided is attributed to various factors. MBA students who are absorbed in their academic pursuits perceive their engagement levels more positively due to a solid commitment to their studies and the pursuit of knowledge. Intrinsic motivation sustains their aspiration to succeed in their academic objectives, leading to a higher level of dedication than industry professionals expect.

MBA students pursuing higher degrees enhance their skills, knowledge, and network, and they consider their current work to support their learning and career goals, increasing their passion and energy for their work, including their sense of achievement and satisfaction. They display a higher sense of loyalty and gratitude to their organization, especially if they receive financial or moral support from their employer. Eventually, they increased their commitment, involvement in their work, and willingness to go above and beyond their duties. Also, MBA students have a lower desire to change their jobs as they confront more challenges and uncertainties in the job market than other employees, upholding their stability and security.

Moreover, MBA students view their academic experience as a tool for shaping their careers. They may show heightened enthusiasm and engagement as they face the challenges presented in their studies. On the other hand, while recognizing MBA students' academic achievements, industry professionals focus more on immediate workplace indicators or specific behavior in professional settings when assessing job engagement. Thus, the perceptual gap between MBA students and Industry Professionals regarding job engagement is rooted in the differing context and criteria each group prioritizes in their evaluations.

Recommendations

The MBA curriculum needs to enrich the curriculum in organizational behavior and communication with an enriched leadership topic that addresses the industry standards in leadership spirit, such as change management, team and conflict management, facilitation skills, and coaching. Also, improvement must occur to promote learning agility based on industry definition. It is time to revise the Strategic Management course to emphasize learning agility, which covers planning, tactics, and strategy topics. There is a need to strengthen the MBA program's alignment of student perception with industry expectations. The program should prioritize career development initiatives and promote stronger industry connections through mentorship programs and networking events. Integrating comprehensive soft skills training into the curriculum is critical for advancing communications, self-awareness, and leadership qualities. Establishing and reinforcing industry partnerships will provide students valuable

exposure to real-world scenarios. The program should encourage open communication channels between students and industry professionals, facilitating forums for constructive feedback to sort out perceptual disparities.

Further, targeted leadership development programs, industry-relevant assessments, and self-reflection practices will give a more accurate perception of students' capabilities. Regularly updating the curriculum to remain responsive to industry changes, providing cross-sectoral experiences, and fostering a culture of life-long learning is essential for ensuring MBA students are well-prepared for dynamic business environments. These recommendations aim to enhance the program's effectiveness and prepare students for successful and impactful careers.

Conclusion

The study illuminates various facets of the perceptions and evaluations surrounding MBA students, illustrating various insights from both Industry Professionals and the self-rating of the MBA students. The alignment in recognizing the drive for high performance as a strength among MBA students depicts the symbiotic relationship between the demanding nature of MBA programs and the industry's expectations. The nuanced difference observed in job engagement, turnover intention, and leadership spirit focuses on the complexity of individual self-perceptions versus external evaluations. These disparities emphasize the importance of effective communication, self-awareness, and a shared understanding between MBA students and Industry Professionals. Bridging these gaps enhances the mutual understanding of expectations and contributes to a more aligned perception of MBA students' strengths and potential. As MBA programs continue to evolve and shape the next generation of business leaders, ongoing collaboration between academia and industry remains crucial for sustaining well-rounded, high-performing professionals who seamlessly integrate into the dynamic landscape of the business.

Conflict of interests

No conflict of interest.

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